

FORMATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCY OF BEGINNER LEVEL STUDENTS

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Annotation: Following our country's independence, there has been a surge in interest in teaching other languages, with several chances for young people. In accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers, new techniques and requirements for foreign language instruction have been devised in the country (CEFR). Textbooks for students in secondary schools and technical institutions, he claims, have been created. Classrooms are outfitted with stands and new information and communication technologies to meet these requirements. This article emphasizes the importance of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the development of English language grammatical competency among pupils at the novice level.

Keywords: Foreign language, grammatical competency, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, techniques.

Learning a foreign language is becoming increasingly popular. Each of the four areas of foreign language science (reading, reading, listening comprehension, and speaking) provides specific concepts and skills. The successful use of current information technology in the educational process is known as educational technology. It also strives to increase the quality and efficacy of education by incorporating cutting-edge technology into the learning process. There are various benefits to adopting such information and communication technology to study a foreign language in particular.

The knowledge and abilities to utilize English in four interrelated skills: speaking, listening, reading, and writing, are referred to as language competences. Collaborative learning is a method of teaching in which students are grouped together to work on a project, assignment, or activity. There are necessary seven skills:

- Collaboration
- Communication
- Creativity
- Critical Thinking

- Character
- Citizenship
- Computational Thinking

If we feel that our job as teachers is to help students develop skills that will help them succeed in the future, we should provide opportunities for them to do so. The individual learned the language in early life and continues to speak it. The person has a natural understanding of the language. The person has the ability to speak fluently and spontaneously. In many social circumstances, the individual is communicatively competent.

Modern technology plays a critical role in language learning and teaching. Every facet of learning a foreign language benefits from the use of technology (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, it is impossible to listen and understand without the use of a computer, a player, and CDs. One of the most fundamental aspects of language learning is listening. This necessitates the student's simultaneous focus on the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings. The ability of pupils to understand and use information and communication technologies is a significant aspect in the usage of new technology in education.

One of the most efficient ways to teach and learn a foreign language is to use modern technologies. Included in this process are:

- When using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language.
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs;
- CD players are available.

Students will find the process of learning a foreign language more engaging and productive if they employ these resources. Interactive games are becoming more common in schools today. It's common understanding that a range of play-based activities can help children demonstrate their abilities, focus, expand their knowledge and skills, and strengthen their bodies. The action that stimulates and accelerates the pupil is the foundation of using gaming technology.

The psychological mechanics of playful action, according to psychologists, are based on the individual's intrinsic needs to express themselves, find a solid place in life, self-manage, and reach their potential. The universally understood ideas and strategies of education should be at the heart of any game. The subjects should be the focus of learning games. During the games, the student is more engaged in the activity than in a regular class, and he or she works more efficiently. It's worth noting that the game is first and foremost a teaching tool.

Playful lessons pique students' interest, and they try to win, therefore the teacher uses them to educate the students. The student wants to believe that he or she can play, speak, listen to, comprehend, and write in English.

In conclusion, Students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and capacity to answer quickly and accurately improve when new methods are used in English teaching. Such techniques pique a student's interest in learning. The learner makes every effort to be well-prepared for the lessons. Students become active participants in the learning process as a result of this. We will contribute to the future creation of effective ways for future instructors to effectively use innovative technology, as the educational system strives to cultivate a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature individual.

REFERENCES:

1. Kennedy, C. Innovation in language teaching and learning. Evaluation of the management of change in ELT projects. Applied Linguistics, // 1988. 39–42.p
2. Markee, N. (1997). Managing curricular innovation. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press. 145-p
3. Murray, D. E. (Ed.). (2008). Planning change, changing plans: Innovations in second language teaching. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
4. Rogers, E. (2003). The diffusion of innovations (5th ed.). New York, NY: Free Press.
5. Van den Branden, K. (Ed.). (2006). Task-based language education: From theory to practice. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press